

Solving the System of Equations Using Polar Coordinates

Abdullayev Sarvar Anvar o'g'li

Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute

Xolmurodov Behzod Botir o'g'li

Phd student of BuxDU

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Annotation: This work is devoted to the solution of some systems of equations in elementary mathematics using the polar coordinate system. In mathematics, solving some systems of equations in the usual way gives us a number of problems, and solving such systems of equations using a polar coordinate system helps us find the answer much easier. The article first provides information about the polar coordinate system and provides several examples.

Keywords: Polar coordinate system, generalized polar coordinate system, scale, polar axis.

As we know, to determine the position of a point, a Cartesian coordinate system with right angles is used. In addition to this system, there are several other coordinate systems.

For example: One of them is the polar coordinate system, which greatly simplifies the solution of many problems and examples.

Using this system, the position of a point on a plane is determined by specifying a point called a pole, a ray called the polar axis extending from that point, and a scale to measure the length. In addition, when specifying the polar system, you should also indicate which rotations around the point are considered positive. Generally, counterclockwise turns are considered positive.

If the polar angle moves counterclockwise from the polar axis, it is considered positive, and if clockwise, it is considered negative. We agree to understand an angle as an angle in trigonometry, that is, we look at this angle up to its sign. and are called the polar coordinates of the point and are written on the drawing. the value of the polar angle of a point satisfying the inequalities is called the principal value of its polar angle.

According to the above, the inequality is valid for polar coordinates. You can also not put such a condition on polar coordinates. In this case, when , it is considered that it has changed from to. When the angle changes from to, the polar coordinate system is called a generalized polar coordinate system.

1-picture

Graph of the polar coordinate system.

In the polar coordinate system, the position of any point M on the plane is determined by the distance $OM = \rho$ between this point and the pole head O and the angle $\angle AOM = \varphi$ between OM and the polar axis OA.

$\rho = OM$ is called the polar radius of point M, and the angle φ is called the polar angle of point M. Taking into account the sign of the angle, an accuracy of up to $\pm 2\pi k$ can be obtained. Thus, the polar coordinates of point M are written in the form $M(\rho; \varphi)$. Among the possible values of the polar angle of point M, select the exact value that satisfies the inequality $-\pi < \varphi \leq \pi$, and call this value the main value

we call it. If the polar coordinates r and φ vary from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$, the polar coordinate system is called a generalized polar coordinate system.

2-picture Cartesian with polar coordinate system connection graph of the coordinate system

Now let's consider the problem that if the polar coordinates of a point are known, its Cartesian coordinates should be calculated, and vice versa, if the Cartesian coordinates of a point are known, its polar coordinates should be calculated.

Let's say that the pole of the polar coordinate system coincides with the origin of the rectangular Cartesian coordinate system, and the polar axis coincides with the positive half of the abscissas (2-picture). Let M be an arbitrary point of the plane, let $(x; y)$ be its Cartesian coordinates, and let $(\rho; \varphi)$ be its polar coordinates.

There is an

$$\begin{cases} x = \rho \cos \varphi \\ y = \rho \sin \varphi \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

relationship between these coordinates. Based on these formulas:

$$x^2 + y^2 = \rho^2 \quad (2)$$

$$\varphi = \arctg \frac{y}{x} \quad (3)$$

relations can be written.

Problem-1. Find the distance d between points $M_1(\rho_1; \varphi_1)$ and $M_2(\rho_2; \varphi_2)$ in the polar coordinate system.

Solution: Based on the theorem of cosines:

$$d^2 = OM_1^2 + OM_2^2 - 2OM_1 \cdot OM_2 \cdot \cos \varphi \quad \text{in this } \varphi = \varphi_2 - \varphi_1$$

$$d^2 = \rho_1^2 + \rho_2^2 - 2\rho_1 \cdot \rho_2 \cdot \cos(\varphi_2 - \varphi_1) \text{ or } d = \sqrt{\rho_1^2 + \rho_2^2 - 2\rho_1 \cdot \rho_2 \cdot \cos(\varphi_2 - \varphi_1)}$$

will be (picture 3).

Picture 3

Points M_1 and M_2 in the polar coordinate system graph of the distance between

Problem-2: This

$$\begin{cases} (u^2 + v^2)(u + v) = 15uv \\ (u^4 + v^4)(u^2 + v^2) = 85u^2v^2 \end{cases}$$

solve the system of equations.

Solution:
$$\begin{cases} (u^2 + v^2)^2(u^2 + v^2 + 2uv) = 225(uv)^2 \\ ((u^2 + v^2)^2 - 2u^2v^2)(u^2 + v^2) = 85(uv)^2 \end{cases}$$

Marking it as

$$\begin{cases} u = r\cos\varphi \\ v = r\sin\varphi \end{cases}$$

we switch the system to the polar coordinate system and put it in place based on the designations.

$$\begin{cases} r^4(r^2 + 2r^2\cos\varphi\sin\varphi) = 225r^4\sin^2\varphi\cos^2\varphi \\ r^6(1 - 2\sin^2\varphi\cos^2\varphi) = 85r^4\sin^2\varphi\cos^2\varphi \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} r^2(1 + \sin 2\varphi) = \frac{225}{4}\sin^2 2\varphi \\ r^2\left(1 - \frac{1}{2}\sin^2 2\varphi\right) = \frac{85}{4}\sin^2 2\varphi \end{cases}$$

We divide the two equalities in the system. Using trigonometric formulas, we find $\sin\varphi$ and $\cos\varphi$, which we need to find the unknown coefficients:

$$\frac{1 + \sin 2\varphi}{1 - \frac{1}{2}\sin^2 2\varphi} = \frac{45}{17} \Rightarrow 17 + 17\sin 2\varphi = 45 - \frac{45}{2}\sin^2 2\varphi$$

$$45\sin^2 2\varphi + 34\sin 2\varphi - 56 = 0$$

$$\sin 2\varphi = t$$

$$45t^2 + 34t - 56 = 0$$

$$t_1 = -\frac{14}{9}; t_2 = \frac{4}{5}$$

$$\sin 2\varphi \neq -\frac{14}{9}; \sin 2\varphi = \frac{4}{5}; \cos 2\varphi = \sqrt{1 - \sin^2 2\varphi} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{16}{25}} = \frac{3}{5};$$

$$\cos 2\varphi = 1 - 2\sin^2 \varphi = \frac{3}{5} \Rightarrow \sin \varphi = \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}; \cos \varphi = \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}}$$

we find r by putting the found angles in the system.

$$r^2(1 + \sin 2\varphi) = \frac{225}{4} \sin^2 2\varphi$$

$$r^2 \left(1 + \frac{4}{5}\right) = \frac{225}{4} \cdot \frac{16}{25} \Rightarrow r = 2\sqrt{5}$$

we find u and v by assigning the found numbers.

$$u = r \cos \varphi = 2\sqrt{5} \cdot \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} = 4$$

$$v = r \sin \varphi = 2\sqrt{5} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} = 2$$

since the variables are mutually symmetric, (2;4) is also a solution of the system. Since the given system and the product are symmetric, the solution (0;0) also satisfies the system

Answer: (0;0), (4;2), (2;4)

Problem-3:

$$\begin{cases} \sqrt[3]{x-y} = \sqrt{x-y} \\ \sqrt[3]{x+y} = \sqrt{x+y-4} \end{cases}$$

solve the system of equations.

Solution: Marking

$$\begin{cases} \sqrt{x-y} = r \cos \varphi \\ \sqrt{x+y-4} = r \sin \varphi \end{cases} \text{ we switch the system to the polar coordinate system } \Rightarrow \begin{cases} x-y = r^2 \cos^2 \varphi \\ x+y = 4 + r^2 \sin^2 \varphi \end{cases}$$

will be set instead

$$\begin{cases} \sqrt[3]{r^2 \cos^2 \varphi} = r \cos \varphi \\ \sqrt[3]{r^2 \sin^2 \varphi + 4} = r \sin \varphi \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} r^2 \cos^2 \varphi = r^3 \cos^3 \varphi \\ r^2 \sin^2 \varphi + 4 = r^3 \sin^3 \varphi \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} r^2 \cos^2 \varphi (1 - r \cos \varphi) = 0 \\ r^3 \sin^3 \varphi - r^2 \sin^2 \varphi - 4 = 0 \end{cases} \Rightarrow$$

$$\begin{cases} r_1 \cos \varphi_1 = 0 \\ r_2 \cos \varphi_2 = 1 \end{cases}$$

$$r^3 \sin^3 \varphi - r^2 \sin^2 \varphi - 4 = 0$$

$$r \sin \varphi = t$$

$$t^3 - t^2 - 4 = 0$$

$$t^3 - 8 - t^2 + 4 = 0$$

$$(t-2)(t^2 + 2t + 4) - (t-2)(t+2) = 0$$

$$(t-2)(t^2 + t + 2) = 0; t=2; \Rightarrow r \sin \varphi = 2$$

$$\begin{cases} r_1 \cos \varphi_1 = 0 \\ r_1 \sin \varphi_1 = 2 \end{cases} \text{ va } \begin{cases} r_2 \cos \varphi_2 = 1 \\ r_2 \sin \varphi_2 = 2 \end{cases}$$

we find the unknown coefficients by putting the found ones into the determined ones

$$\text{I. } \begin{cases} \sqrt{x-y} = 0 \\ \sqrt{x+y-4} = 2 \end{cases} \Rightarrow + \begin{cases} x-y = 0 \\ x+y = 8 \end{cases} \begin{matrix} 2x=8; \\ \end{matrix} \begin{cases} x_1 = 4 \\ y_1 = 4 \end{cases}$$

$$\text{II. } \begin{cases} \sqrt{x-y} = 1 \\ \sqrt{x+y-4} = 2 \end{cases} \Rightarrow + \begin{cases} x-y = 1 \\ x+y = 8 \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} x_2 = 4,5 \\ y_2 = 3,5 \end{cases}$$

Answer: (4; 4); (4,5; 3,5)

Problem-4: This

$$\begin{cases} x^{-1} + y^{-1} = 5 \\ x^{-2} + y^{-2} = 13 \end{cases}$$

solve the system of equations

Solution: In order to solve this system in the polar coordinate system, we enter $\begin{cases} x = r \cos \varphi \\ y = r \sin \varphi \end{cases}$

$$\begin{cases} \frac{1}{r \cos \varphi} + \frac{1}{r \sin \varphi} = 5 \\ \frac{1}{r^2 \cos^2 \varphi} + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \varphi} = 13 \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{2(\cos \varphi + \sin \varphi)}{\sin 2\varphi} \right) = 5 \\ \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{4}{\sin^2 2\varphi} \right) = 13 \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \frac{2}{5}(\cos \varphi + \sin \varphi) = r \sin 2\varphi \\ \frac{4}{13} = r^2 \sin^2 2\varphi \end{cases}$$

$$\Rightarrow \begin{cases} r \sin 2\varphi = \frac{2}{\sqrt{13}} \\ \frac{2}{5}(\cos \varphi + \sin \varphi) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{13}} \end{cases}$$

$$(\cos \varphi + \sin \varphi)^2 = \left(\frac{5}{\sqrt{13}} \right)^2$$

$$\cos^2 \varphi + 2 \sin \varphi \cos \varphi + \sin^2 \varphi = \frac{25}{13}$$

$$1 + \sin 2\varphi = \frac{25}{13} \Rightarrow \sin 2\varphi = \frac{12}{13};$$

$$\cos 2\varphi = \sqrt{1 - \sin^2 2\varphi} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{144}{169}} = \frac{5}{13}$$

$$\cos 2\varphi = 1 - 2\sin^2 \varphi = \frac{5}{13} \Rightarrow \sin \varphi = \frac{2}{\sqrt{13}};$$

$$\cos \varphi = \sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \varphi} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{4}{13}} = \frac{3}{\sqrt{13}};$$

$$r \sin 2\varphi = \frac{2}{\sqrt{13}} \text{ from being } r \cdot \frac{12}{13} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{13}} \Rightarrow r = \frac{\sqrt{13}}{6}$$

$$x = r \cos \varphi = \frac{\sqrt{13}}{6} \cdot \frac{3}{\sqrt{13}} = \frac{1}{2};$$

$$y = r \sin \varphi = \frac{\sqrt{13}}{6} \cdot \frac{2}{\sqrt{13}} = \frac{1}{3};$$

since the variables are symmetric, $\left(\frac{1}{3}; \frac{1}{2}\right)$ is also a solution of the system

Answer: $\left(\frac{1}{2}; \frac{1}{3}\right)$ va $\left(\frac{1}{3}; \frac{1}{2}\right)$.

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